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Optogenetics for neural transplant manipulation and functional analysis

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ABSTRACT

Transplantation of neural stem cells (NSCs) or NSC-derived neurons into the brain is a promising therapeutic approach to restore neuronal function. Rapid progress in the NSCs research field, particularly due to the exploitation of induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs), offers great potential and an unlimited source of stem cell-derived neural grafts. Studying the functional integration of these grafts into host brain tissues and their effects on each other have been boosted by the implementation of optogenetic technologies. Optogenetics provides high spatiotemporal functional manipulations of grafted or host neurons in parallel. This review aims to highlight the impact of optogenetics in neural stem cell transplantations.

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1. Introduction

Neurological disorders such as chronic neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Parkinson's disease, or acute brain damage due to stroke and traumatic brain injuries are accompanied by loss of neurons or supporting glia cells that have severe effects on the patient's quality of life [1,2]. Unlike in many animal models, the endogenous regeneration capacity of the human brain is very limited [3]. Therefore, as a treatment option, cell or tissue replacement approaches are extensively evaluated to compensate for damaged neural tissue [4,5]. Neural stem cells (NSCs) are the progenitors of many different types of neurons. Adult NSCs are generated in restricted regions of the adult brain located at the subventricular zone (SVZ) and hippocampal subgranular zone (SGZ). These cells possess the self-renewal and differentiation capability into neurons, astrocytes or oligodendrocytes [5].

Endogenous adult NSCs, embryonic stem cells (ESCs) and induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) are the three major sources of neural stem cells, Fig. 1. ESCs are derived from the inner cell mass of blastocysts [6]. ESCs are highly proliferative that can be differentiated into desired cell types and therefore are commonly used in

cell regeneration and replacement therapies to revive lost neural function [7]. However, due to ethical concerns, ESC applications are limited or forbidden in many countries. Human iPSCs are generated by reprogramming somatic cells into pluripotent stem cells that can further be differentiated *in vitro* into cell types of interest Fig. 1, [8]. Human iPSCs are also an unlimited source for neural grafts and have reduced ethical concerns. These cells can directly be derived from patients Fig. 1, which avoids immunogenicity upon transplantation. Cells from an allogeneic donor express foreign human leucocyte antigens (HLA), which can lead to immunological rejection [9,10]. Patient-derived or iPSCs from matching homozygous HLA donors are well-suited for personalized medicine [11].

Stem cell-based replacement therapies have been applied in various animal models for different applications ranging from improving the impaired function to replacing the lost tissue [12]. Transplanted cells have been showed to survive extended time periods *in vivo*, however further studies are required to evaluate whether these cells are morphologically and functionally integrated and whether this integration is beneficial to the recovery of damaged neural circuit [13]. Traditional methods to understand graft-host integration were mainly based on applying electrical stimuli and recording with electrophysiological methods. However, these methods do not provide enough spatiotemporal resolution to study largescale graft-host neural circuit's interactions [3]. By optogenetic approaches, it is now possible to efficiently and non-invasively track integration of the graft *in vivo* and more importantly to improve neuronal function [14].

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Fig. 1. Human iPSC- and ESC-derived NSCs can be differentiated into neural cell types in monolayers, spheroids or organoids and subsequently transplanted into host brains. Human iPSCs are derived from fibroblasts taken from patients or healthy donors. ESCs are derived from the inner mass of blastocysts.

Optogenetics represents the application of light stimuli to control cellular behavior, e.g., neural activity, in the genetically modified cells that express optically sensitive actuators [15]. Optogenetics offer great temporal resolution at milliseconds scales that makes it an optimal technology to study neural circuit function *in vivo* or *in vitro* [16,17]. The genetic information of optogenetic tools can be delivered and expressed in a cell-type-specific manner using viral tools or transgenic animals [18]. The expression of optogenetic actuators in NSCs and transplants is achieved accordingly [19,20]. Thereby, one can track neural stem cells expressing optogenetic actuators after transplantation and stimulate specifically the neurons expressing actuators via transcranial or implanted optical illumination without targeting host neurons [13].

1.1. Optogenetic actuators

Opsins contain seven transmembrane domains and their all-trans retinal chromophore is isomerized by light illumination [21]. Most commonly used optogenetic tools are ion-transferring channels like Channelrhodopsins (ChRs) or ion-transferring pumps like halorhodopsin (NpHR), red light-drivable halorhodopsin (Jaws) and archaerhodopsin (Arch) [22–24]. Activated

channelrhodopsins transfer ions passively based on their electrochemical gradients. Light-induced ChR2 activation leads to an inward current of sodium (Na^+) and calcium (Ca^{2+}) cations that causes membrane depolarization, and triggers action potentials if a firing threshold is passed [25]. Optogenetic pumps on the other hand exploit photon energy to pump ions against their electrochemical gradient. Optogenetic pumps either pump protons outside of the cytosol (Arch), or pump negatively charged chloride ions (Cl^-) into the cytosol (NpHR or Jaws) [25,26]. These tools cause membrane hyperpolarization and thereby inhibit electrically excitable cells like neurons [26].

Targeted mutagenesis of these optogenetic proteins or the creation of chimeras have extended the optogenetic toolboxes and improved their biophysical features such as channel kinetics, photocurrent magnitude, spectral sensitivity and membrane trafficking [27]. Among many examples of channelrhodopsins there are ChRs with faster temporal kinetics (e.g. ChETA), ChRs with red-shifted excitation spectra (e.g. ChRimson), and ChRs with stabilized open conducting state of their channels so called Step function or bi-stable opsins (SFOs) [28]. Anion-conducting ChRs have been engineered by targeted mutagenesis on cation-conducting ChR2 chimera C1C2 including blue-light activated cell silencing iC1C2

[29]. Activated light-gated optogenetic anion channels passively transfer anions based on naturally occurring electrochemical gradients [30]. Later highly anion-selective ChRs like iC⁺⁺ and their step function version SwiChR⁺⁺ have been engineered [31]. These advances have been used to stimulate or inhibit grafted neurons with higher temporal resolutions by expressing actuators with faster channel kinetics [16,27].

1.2. Light-delivery options for optogenetic stimulation of transplanted neurons

Light-delivery with optimized temporal and spatial resolution as well as sufficient but safe power levels to avoid tissue damage is a critical aspect of *in vitro* and *in vivo* optogenetics. Lasers and light-emitting diodes (LEDs) are major sources of light in optogenetics [32]. Optical stimulation by one-photon wide-field illumination using LED-light is commonly used in optogenetics. To improve the spatial resolution of one-photon stimulation system LEDs are replaced by micro-LEDs or laser light [17]. However, one-photon stimulation often is used for mesoscale optogenetic stimulation of neural circuits [33]. Two-photon stimulation, by concomitant absorption of two photons, offers improved spatial resolution and deeper penetration in scattering tissue. By using spatial light modulators (SLM) or holographic projections, it is possible to split a two-photon beam on several spots in the imaging plan and therefore stimulate specified neurons in a local circuit [34]. For *in vivo* stimulation in freely moving animals, mostly a fiber-guided laser delivers light through chronically implanted cannulas or alternatively high-power LEDs are used for optical stimulations [34]. For chronic photostimulation of deeper brain regions, optical fibers are required to be invasively implanted that can cause mechanical damages to the brain tissue. With advances on transcranial photostimulation optogenetics hold promises for non-invasive stimulation/inhibition of transplanted neurons [35]. Furthermore, combining optogenetics with electrophysiological recordings from both implanted and host neurons enables to monitor functional integration and synaptic communication between implanted and host neurons [35].

1.3. Recording neural graft-host functional interactions using optogenetic tools

Optogenetic *in vivo* applications led to the development of advanced instruments for simultaneous optical stimulation and electrophysiological recording [34]. Previous methods to record optogenetically-evoked *in vivo* neuronal activity included single or multiunit patch clamp or implanted multi-electrode arrays (MEAs) recordings [36]. Dual optical and electrical probes, so called optrodes, have been developed in different configurations and designs by incorporating several electrical recording and light stimulation sites for simultaneous stimulation of and recording from neural populations [37]. However, recording from multiple genetically identified neurons using electrophysiological tools is challenging. This issue has been resolved by the development of genetically encoded calcium indicators (GECIs) like GCaMP [38]. GECIs can target particular subcellular compartments such as synapse and axon or target specific cell types and populations that allows continuous single cell or population level recordings from hundreds of neurons [38]. Recording from local neural ensembles in freely moving or head-fixed animals using GECIs fluorescent imaging made it possible to connect optogenetics and network electrophysiology with behavioral studies [39,40]. Functional integration of the transplanted neurons can also be studied using non-invasive whole brain high-field functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) that makes it possible to explore graft-host

functional integration both at local transplantation site and at remote downstream targets across the whole brain [4]. Regarding the non-invasive nature of fMRI readouts it is possible to follow-up long-term functional integration of the grafted neurons after transplantation, but not with single cell resolution [13]. The activity of transplanted and host neurons can be recorded in *ex vivo* settings by non-invasive *in vitro* MEA chips that capture extracellular neural activity using planar electrodes [41–43]. Piña-Crespo *et al.* applied this method and injected hESC-derived ChR2 or NpHR expressing neurons into rat hippocampal slices on MEA chips [44]. The graft-host synaptic communication was confirmed two weeks post-transplantation by recording optogenetically-evoked high frequency oscillations (10Hz–100Hz) from host neural circuits [44].

2. Optogenetics for functional analysis and manipulation of transplanted neurons

One of the first examples of transplanted NSCs-derived ChR2-expressing neurons to the brain is the work by Weick *et al.* [6]. After *in vitro* optimizations, neurons expressing ChR2 were grafted into the ventricular zone of neonatal mice. Transplanted neurons were distinguished by optogenetic tracking of ChR2 linked to mCherry fluorophore. Synaptic communication between grafted and host neurons was confirmed by optogenetic stimulation of the transplanted neurons and the recording of post-synaptic currents in host neurons [6], Fig. 2. Optogenetics have been exploited to track the morphological structure of transplanted neurons and to decipher their functional integration with host neural circuits, astrocytes and oligodendrocytes [13,45]. For functional studies, optogenetic tools are used for 1) demonstrating the presence of mutual synaptic communication between transplanted neurons and host neurons, 2) controlling activity of the host neural circuits by modulating activity of the implanted neurons, 3) restoring impaired neural function through chronic stimulation-dependent recovery [12,45], 4) recovering damaged spinal cord neural circuits and thereby control muscular function by engrafted motor neurons [49], 5) replacing retinal photoreceptors to restore visual function [50], and 6) studying *in vivo* transplanted brain organoids [51], Fig. 2. Following sections summarize previous work on above-mentioned applications.

2.1. Controlling host neural function by transplanted neurons expressing inhibitory actuators

Functional integration of transplanted neurons in the host brains and spinal cords has been confirmed using NpHR. In an *ex vivo/in vivo* model Tønnesen *et al.* transplanted mouse NSCs-derived neurons into the organotypic striatal cultures or striatum of the CD-1 mice, which have damaged dopaminergic neurons [14]. After expressing ChR2 or NpHR either in grafted or in host neurons Tønnesen *et al.* applied different stimulation or inhibition protocols to confirm bi-directional connectivity between graft-host neural circuits [14]. Later, Steinbeck *et al.* grafted hESCs-derived eNpHR-expressing dopaminergic neurons to the substantia nigra of mice with lesion-induced Parkinsonian motor deficits [12]. Transplanted dopaminergic neurons improved motor deficits within 16 weeks post-transplantation, Fig. 2b. Optogenetic selective silencing of the grafted dopaminergic neurons instantly returned the motor deficits symptoms, a reversible effect that was blocked by dopamine agonist, and confirmed optogenetic-induced dopaminergic communication between graft-host neural circuits [12].

Fig. 2. Optogenetic stimulation targeting transplanted or host neurons in brain, spinal cord and retina. a) Glutamatergic neurons expressing Chr2 grafted into peri-ischemic regions after stroke. Optical stimulation indirectly increased firing rate of host neurons through synaptic communication [45]. b) eNpHR-expressing dopaminergic neurons transplanted to Parkinsonian brain and optical stimulation exploited to inhibit motor deficits [12]. c) Chr2-expressing GABAergic neurons grafted into epileptic hippocampus to optically silence its hyperexcitability [35,46,47]. d) eNpHR-expressing GABAergic neurons have not been studied in neural transplantation studies, however it has been tried *in vivo* to decipher circuit functions [48]. e) Optogenetic stimulation of Chr2 expressing host neurons to promote differentiation and survival of the grafted excitatory or inhibitory neurons [46]. f) Chr2-expressing motor neurons implanted in spinal cord are optically stimulated to control muscle function [49]. g) Engineered eNpHR or Jaws expressing photoreceptors implanted into a blind retina. By illuminating these photoreceptors transfer eNpHR and Jaws-related signals into bipolar and retinal ganglion cells [50].

2.2. Controlling abnormal function of the host brain by grafted GABAergic neurons

A possible therapeutic approach for neurological disorders with hyper excitable neural activity, e.g., epilepsy, is to enhance GABAergic inhibition to suppress hyperexcitability [35]. Inhibitory GABAergic neurons derived from NSCs transplanted to the epileptic brain can be equipped with optogenetic actuators to control the activity of the epileptic regions using a light beam [35,46,47]. Cunningham *et al.* grafted Chr2 expressing GABAergic interneurons derived from human stem cells into the mice epileptic hippocampus that suppressed seizure and behavioral abnormalities either by spontaneous firing or by optical stimulation. Electrophysiology data showed that optogenetic stimulation of the grafted GABAergic neurons induced GABAergic postsynaptic responses in the epileptic hippocampal neurons [35], Fig. 2c. The required time for differentiation, maturation and functional integration of the hiPSC-derived GABAergic neurons in the host *ex vivo* and *in vivo* neural tissues can be studied by, conversely, expressing Chr2 in the host neurons that enervate the graft. By optical stimulation of the host hippocampal neurons, Avaliani *et al.* demonstrated that an extended time period, about 24 weeks, is required for proper maturation and integration of GABAergic neurons [46], Fig. 2e.

Another source of GABAergic interneurons is medial ganglionic eminence (MGE), a transitory developmental structure at embryonic and fetal stages that produces GABAergic neurons and direct them to the neocortex [52]. Hsieh *et al.* extracted MGE precursor cells from Chr2-positive mouse embryos and transplanted them into neonatal hippocampus of mice [53]. Optogenetic stimulation,

patch clamp recordings and pharmacological interventions have demonstrated that these cells differentiated to GABAergic interneurons and formed synaptic contacts with host excitatory pyramidal neurons in the hippocampus, but not with host inhibitory neurons [53], Fig. 2c.

2.3. Restoring impaired neural function after stroke

NSCs-derived neurons have been extensively used to replace lost neural tissue to restore impaired neural function after stroke and traumatic brain injury [54]. For functional studies, Daadi *et al.* transplanted Chr2 expressing NSCs to the peri-infarct zone of the ischemic rat brain and applied chronic light stimuli for four weeks post-transplantation [45], Fig. 2a. Chronic optogenetic stimulation of the Chr2 expressing NSCs influenced endogenous motor network function and improved sensorimotor performances. Functional recovery was associated with upregulated expression of genes involved in neural differentiation, axonal growth and branching and synaptic plasticity, and downregulated expression of genes involved in the inflammatory response after stroke [45]. Yu *et al.* applied optochemogenetics fusion protein luminopsin 3 (LMO3) to stimulate iPSC-derived neural progenitor cells (NPCs) graft in mice stroke model [36]. LMO3 is a fusion protein containing luciferase, Gaussia luciferase (sbGLuc), and a light-sensitive opsin, VolvoxChannelrhodopsin 1 (VChR1). LMO3 expressing neural circuits were driven by either extrinsic physical light or intrinsic biological light, bioluminescence [36]. Yu *et al.* activated transplanted NPCs upon photostimulation and luciferase substrate coelenterazine (CTZ) administration. Optogenetic stimulation of or

CTZ administration to the post-ischemic brain slices for 5 days or *in vivo* applications led to enhanced axonal myelination, neuroplasticity, improved neural connectivity at thalamocortical circuits, and functional recovery [36].

2.4. Applications of optogenetic neuronal grafts in the damaged spinal cord

Optogenetic stimulation of stem cell-derived neurons or glia in the other neural systems like spinal cord have been tested. For instance, Ono *et al.* after confirming that optical stimulation of glia progenitor cells expressing ChR2 (OS3-ChR2) triggers their differentiation to oligodendrocytes, injected OS3-ChR2 cells into the spinal cord of mouse models with lysophosphatidyl choline (LPC)-induced demyelination. Optical stimulation of the OS3-ChR2 cells for 72 h alleviated demyelination and improved motor performance [55]. To improve chronic survival of the grafted motor neurons *in vivo*, Bryson *et al.* developed genetically modified murine ESC-derived motor neurons expressing ChR2 plus glia-derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF) [49], Fig. 2f. They transplanted embryoid bodies containing ChR2-expressing motor neurons to the distal part of the ligated sciatic nerve. Transplanted motor neurons extended their axons branches toward distal and proximal directions and their axons were myelinated over five weeks. Optical stimulation of grafted motor neurons with short light pulses produced muscle twitches and stimulation with higher frequencies produced tetanic contraction in the enervated muscles that confirmed functional integration of motor neurons in neuromuscular circuitry [49].

2.5. Applications of optogenetic photoreceptors to restore visual function

Replacing damaged or lost photoreceptors for treatment of retinal degenerative diseases is challenging because of difficulties in generating functional photoreceptors with light-sensitive outer segment and integration of transplanted photoreceptors with retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) [56]. Optogenetic-photoreceptors can be exploited as an alternative approach that does not require outer segment development or integration with RPE [56]. Garita-Hernandez *et al.* generated optogenetic photoreceptors either by injecting adeno-associated viral (AAV) vectors encoding enhanced NpHR into eyes of newborn mice or by expressing Jaws in human iPSCs-derived photoreceptors [50], Fig. 2g. NpHR-expressing photoreceptor precursors and Jaws expressing cone photoreceptors were transplanted into the retinae of blind mice by subretinal injections. Grafted photoreceptors formed synaptic connections with host retinal bipolar cells and transmitted the optogenetically-driven signals to the ON and OFF ganglion cells and activated these cells, Fig. 2g. Combining photoreceptor replacement therapy and optogenetics allowed replacing lost retinal structures with stem cell-derived photoreceptor precursor cells and restoring visual function by optogenetic sensing [50].

2.6. Application of optogenetics in transplanted brain organoids

Optogenetics have also been applied to probe the functionality of *in vivo* grafted brain organoids that are heterogeneous 3D neural tissues generated from hESCs or hiPSCs to recapitulate some features of development and developmental disorders [57]. Cerebral, retinal and brain organoids are lacking sufficient nutrient diffusion into their deeper layers due to the lack of vascularization [57]. For prolonging their survival and maturation as well as studying their interactions with the host brain, transplanting organoids into physiological brain tissue environment of mice has been performed

[58], Fig. 1. Similar to transplanted neural grafts, brain organoids and host neural circuits had functional interactions that were studied by incorporating optogenetic tools into the transplanted organoids [51,59]. Mansour *et al.* transplanted hESCs-derived ChR2-expressing brain organoids into mouse brains. They showed that optical stimulation of the ChR2-expressing organoids induced local field potentials (LFPs) in the host neurons with 20 ms latencies that confirmed excitatory inputs from grafted organoid into the host neurons [51].

3. Conclusion and outlook

Neural progenitor cells and defined neurons derived from hESCs and hiPSCs have been exploited in preclinical studies for the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases. Even though conventional pharmacological interventions can be used to alleviate the symptoms, a major challenge is the progressive nature of the neurological disorders that requires restoration of the lost brain tissue and its function. A promising translational approach is to exploit stem cells transplantation techniques giving rise to replacement and regeneration of the lost brain circuits, recovering impaired neural activity or controlling their abnormal activity. Neural transplantation needs to be accompanied by advanced recording and manipulating technologies. Optogenetics are well suited to stimulate or silence grafted cells and tissues. Yet at an early stage requiring further studies, combining neural grafts with optogenetic tools is a vivid research field and promising for therapeutic applications.

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